

Robin's Inequality for Superabundant Numbers

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Abstract

The Riemann hypothesis is a conjecture that the Riemann zeta function has its zeros only at the negative even integers and complex numbers with real part $\frac{1}{2}$. There are several statements equivalent to the famous Riemann hypothesis. Robin's criterion states that the Riemann hypothesis is true if and only if the inequality $\sigma(n) < e^\gamma \cdot n \cdot \log \log n$ holds for all natural numbers $n > 5040$, where $\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function of n , $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant and \log is the natural logarithm. We require the properties of superabundant numbers, that is to say left to right maxima of $n \mapsto \frac{\sigma(n)}{n}$. It is well-known that the smallest counterexample of the Robin's inequality greater than **5040** must be a superabundant number. In this note, we prove that the Robin's inequality holds for all superabundant numbers greater than **5040**. By reductio ad absurdum, we prove that the Riemann hypothesis is true.

Keywords: Riemann hypothesis, Robin's inequality, Superabundant numbers, Sum-of-divisors function, Prime numbers

MSC Classification: 11M26 , 11A41 , 11A25

1 Introduction

The Riemann hypothesis is considered by many to be the most important unsolved problem in pure mathematics. It was proposed by Bernhard Riemann (1859). The Riemann hypothesis belongs to the Hilbert's eighth problem on David Hilbert's list of twenty-three unsolved problems. This is one of the Clay

2 *The Riemann hypothesis*

Mathematics Institute's Millennium Prize Problems. As usual $\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function of n

$$\sum_{d|n} d,$$

where $d | n$ means the integer d divides n . Define $f(n)$ as $\frac{\sigma(n)}{n}$.

Proposition 1 *For every prime power p^a , we have $f(p^a) = \frac{p^{a+1}-1}{p^a \cdot (p-1)}$, where the function $f(\dots)$ is multiplicative [1, Lemma 2.1 pp. 3]. If p is a prime number, and a, b two positive integers, then [1, pp. 5]:*

$$f(p^{a+b}) - f(p^a) \cdot f(p^b) = -\frac{(p^a - 1) \cdot (p^b - 1)}{p^{a+b-1} \cdot (p-1)^2}.$$

Proposition 2 [2, Proposition 2 pp. 210]. *For all natural numbers $n \geq 7$:*

$$\frac{f(n)}{\log \log n} \leq \frac{f(12)}{\log \log 12} < 2.57.$$

We say that $\text{Robin}(n)$ holds provided that

$$f(n) < e^\gamma \cdot \log \log n,$$

where $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant and \log is the natural logarithm. This is known as the Robin's inequality. The Ramanujan's Theorem states that if the Riemann hypothesis is true, then the Robin's inequality holds for large enough n . Next, we have the Robin's Theorem:

Proposition 3 *$\text{Robin}(n)$ holds for all natural numbers $n > 5040$ if and only if the Riemann hypothesis is true [2, Theorem 1 pp. 188].*

It is known that $\text{Robin}(n)$ holds for many classes of natural numbers n .

Proposition 4 *$\text{Robin}(n)$ holds for all natural numbers $n > 5040$ such that $p \leq e^{31.018189471}$, where p is the largest prime factor of n [3, Theorem 4.2 pp. 748].*

We recall that an integer n is said to be squarefull if for every prime factor p of n we have $p^2 | n$.

Proposition 5 *$\text{Robin}(n)$ holds for all natural numbers $n > 5040$ when they are squarefull [4, Theorem 1.4 pp. 358].*

Superabundant numbers were defined by Leonidas Alaoglu and Paul Erdős (1944). Let $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3, \dots, p_k$ denote the first k consecutive primes, then

an integer of the form $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{a_i}$ with $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k \geq 1$ is called a Hardy-Ramanujan integer [4, pp. 367]. A natural number n is called superabundant precisely when, for all natural numbers $m < n$

$$f(m) < f(n).$$

We know the following property for the superabundant numbers:

Proposition 6 *If n is superabundant, then n is a Hardy-Ramanujan integer [5, Theorem 1 pp. 450].*

Several analogues of the Riemann hypothesis have already been proved. Many authors expect (or at least hope) that it is true. However, there are some implications in case of the Riemann hypothesis might be false.

Proposition 7 *The smallest counterexample of the Robin's inequality greater than 5040 must be a superabundant number [6, Theorem 3 pp. 273].*

Putting all together yields the proof of the Riemann hypothesis since we show that such smallest counterexample of the Robin's inequality greater than 5040 does not actually exist.

2 Main Results

This is the main insight.

Lemma 8 *Let n be a superabundant number such that $p_k > e^{31.018189471}$, where p_k is the largest prime factor of n and the k th prime. Then*

$$f(n^2) > f(n) + 2.57 \cdot \log 2.$$

Proof For every prime power p^a , we have

$$f(p^{2 \cdot a}) - f(p^a) \cdot f(p^a) = -\frac{(p^a - 1)^2}{p^{2 \cdot a - 1} \cdot (p - 1)^2}$$

by Proposition 1. In this way, we obtain that

$$\frac{f(p^{2 \cdot a})}{f(p^a)} = f(p^a) - \frac{(p^a - 1)^2}{f(p^a) \cdot p^{2 \cdot a - 1} \cdot (p - 1)^2}.$$

The minimum value of the expression

$$f(p^a) - \frac{(p^a - 1)^2}{f(p^a) \cdot p^{2 \cdot a - 1} \cdot (p - 1)^2}$$

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is reached exactly when $a = 1$. Since $f(\dots)$ is multiplicative, then the following inequality

$$\frac{f(n^2)}{f(n)} \geq \frac{f(N_k^2)}{f(N_k)}$$

holds because of n is a superabundant number by Proposition 6, where $N_k = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i$ is the primorial number of order k . However, we have

$$\frac{f(N_k^2)}{f(N_k)} = \prod_{i=1}^k \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_i \cdot (p_i + 1)}\right)$$

is strictly increasing and

$$1 + \frac{2.57 \cdot \log 2}{f(N_k)} = 1 + 2.57 \cdot (\log 2) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^k \frac{p_i}{p_i + 1}$$

is strictly decreasing, where we know that

$$1 + \frac{2.57 \cdot \log 2}{f(N_k)} \geq 1 + \frac{2.57 \cdot \log 2}{f(n)}$$

holds by the properties of the function $f(\dots)$ using the Proposition 1. By a trivial numerical calculation, we check that

$$\frac{f(N_k^2)}{f(N_k)} > 1 + \frac{2.57 \cdot \log 2}{f(N_k)}$$

holds for all $p_k \geq 79$. Therefore, this result is strong enough for $p_k > e^{31.018189471}$. □

This is the main theorem.

Theorem 9 *The Riemann hypothesis is true.*

Proof Suppose that n is the smallest counterexample of the Robin's inequality greater than 5040. The value of n is a superabundant number by Proposition 7. Let $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{a_i}$ be the representation of this superabundant number n as the product of the first k consecutive primes $p_1 < \dots < p_k$ with the natural numbers $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k \geq 1$ as exponents, since n must be a Hardy-Ramanujan integer by Proposition 6. Under our assumption, we have

$$f(n) \geq e^\gamma \cdot \log \log n.$$

We know that $\text{Robin}(n^2)$ holds by Proposition 5. In this way, we obtain that

$$e^\gamma > \frac{f(n^2)}{\log \log n^2}.$$

Consequently, we can see that

$$f(n) > \frac{f(n^2)}{\log \log n^2} \cdot \log \log n.$$

That is the same as

$$f(n) \cdot \frac{\log \log n^2}{\log \log n} > f(n^2).$$

This is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(n) \cdot \frac{\log \log n^2}{\log \log n} &= f(n) \cdot \frac{\log(2 \cdot \log n)}{\log \log n} \\
 &= f(n) \cdot \frac{\log \log n + \log 2}{\log \log n} \\
 &= f(n) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\log 2}{\log \log n} \right) \\
 &= f(n) + \frac{f(n)}{\log \log n} \cdot \log 2 \\
 &< f(n) + 2.57 \cdot \log 2
 \end{aligned}$$

by Proposition 2. Hence, we deduce that

$$f(n) + 2.57 \cdot \log 2 > f(n^2).$$

However, this is indeed false due to Lemma 8 over the Proposition 4. In this way, we obtain a contradiction under the assumption that $\text{Robin}(n)$ fails (i.e. $\text{Robin}(n)$ does not hold). To sum up, the study of this arbitrary superabundant number n reveals that $\text{Robin}(n)$ holds on anyway. Accordingly, $\text{Robin}(n)$ holds for all superabundant numbers n greater than 5040. This contradicts the fact that the smallest counterexample of the Robin's inequality greater than 5040 must be a superabundant number according to Proposition 7. By reductio ad absurdum, we prove that the Riemann hypothesis is true. \square

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